

Tsallis Entropy and Degeneracy

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. June 10, 2023

For a Maxwell-Boltzmann situation, one may consider the number of permutations of N particles with $n(e_i)$ of them having energy e_i i.e. $N! / \text{Product over } i \text{ } n(e_i)!$. In such a case, $n(e_i)!$ removes the degeneracy of the identical $n(e_i)$ particles. In order to convert the degeneracies into a sum, one takes \ln of the number of permutations. In such a case one has $\ln(N!) - \text{Sum over } i \text{ } \ln(n(e_i)!)$. If $N \rightarrow \text{infinite}$, ensuring that $n(e_i)$ values are also large, one may apply Stirling's high n limit to $\ln(n(e_i)!)$ to yield $n(e_i)\ln(n(e_i))$. In information theory $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } n(e_i) \ln(n(e_i))$ is called the average of information where information is given by $n(e_i)$. This average, we argue, is really a sum form of the unnecessary degeneracy information for each $n(e_i)$ and is called entropy. We ask: Is it possible to write a sum of more general degeneracies (other than identical particle permutations) (which should be equivalent to entropy) which, however, in a certain limit become the degeneracy of permutations?

We answer yes if one uses the identity: $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \{p^{(x)} - 1\} / x = \ln(p)$. $p \ln(p)$ is the form of the permutation degeneracy in sum form and so it corresponds to the limit of $x \rightarrow 0$. If x is not 0, one may write a sum of degeneracies depending on $p(i)^x$ which in the limit of $x \rightarrow 0$ become permutation degeneracies. This entropy is called Tsallis entropy and is well-known in the literature (1). We wish to point out that the $p(i)^x$ i.e. probabilities to a constant power seem to represent the degeneracies in the system (in sum form), which in a special limit represent the degeneracy of permuting $n(e_i)$ identical particles i.e. $\ln(n(e_i)!)$ in sum form.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution and Degeneracies

If one considers a probability $p(i)$ for an event to occur and considers trial runs which are based solely on $p(i)$ (e.g. tossing a die) then for $N \rightarrow \text{infinite}$, one expects $Np(i)$ outcomes of i . The probability of a particular set of N trial runs is:

$$\text{Probability for a particular } N \text{ trial run} = \text{Product over } i \text{ } p(i)^{Np(i)} \quad ((1))$$

$p(i)$ may be rewritten as: $\exp\{\ln(p(i))\}$. Taking $\ln(\text{Probability for a trial run}) = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } N p(i) \ln(p(i))$. ((2))

- $\ln[\text{Probability for a trial run}]$ is called entropy (when multiplied by Boltzmann's constant k).

One may note that all N trials have the same probability in the case of $N \rightarrow \text{infinite}$. Thus the probability should be one over the number of arrangements of N particles with $Np(i)=n(i)$. The number of permutations is:

$$\{N! / \text{Product over } i \text{ } n(e_i)!\} \quad ((3))$$

Taking \ln of this value yields: $\ln(N!) - \text{Sum over } i \text{ } \ln(n(i)!)$ ((4))

The \ln converts a product into sums. We ask: What does $n(i)!$ mean physically?

We argue that it represents the degeneracy associated with $n(i)$ identical particles. In such a case, they may be permuted $n(i)!$ ways. $\ln(n(i)!)!$ represents the sum form due to the overall \ln . Thus entropy, we argue, really represents degeneracies in the system presented in the form of a sum. Using Stirling's high n approximation:

$\ln[n(i)!] = n(i) \ln(n(i))$ ((5)) with $\ln(n(i))$ being called information and $n(i)\ln(n(i))$ being part of an average of information.

Information multiplied by $n(i)$ is the "sum" form of degeneracies associated with $n(i)$ identical particles. We ask: Is it possible to have degeneracies which are more complicated than simply the permutation of identical $n(i)$ particles? The answer seems to be yes if one uses an identity for $\ln(p(i))$ i.e.:

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \{ p(i)^x - 1 \} / x = \ln(p(i)) \quad ((6))$$

What is special about the approach of ((6)) is that there is a limiting situation in which the degeneracies become permutations of identical particle permutations which is a physically simple situation.

To see how ((6)) arises, consider $p = \exp(a)$. Then:

RHS: $\exp(ax) - 1$ LHS xa In the $x \rightarrow 0$ limit the RHS becomes, to first order, ax , which matches the LHS. No higher orders are needed in an $x \rightarrow 0$ limit.

In the case of degeneracies which are not simple identical particle permutations, one may suggest that x is a number greater than 0, for example. The next step is to consider a form in which an entropy expression collapses to $\sum_i p(i) \ln(p(i))$ when $x \rightarrow 0$.

Using: $\sum_i p(i) = 1$ and ((6)) one may write:

$$\{ \sum_i p(i) - p(i)^q \} / (q-1) = 1/(q-1) \{ \sum_i p(i) [1 - p(i)^{q-1}] \} \quad ((7))$$

$q-1$ is now equivalent to x , so $q \rightarrow 1$ is the same as $x \rightarrow 0$. ((7)) is called Tsallis entropy and is well known in the literature (1). The point we wish to make is that the form ((7)) is a representation of the degeneracies in the system written in sum form. These degeneracies are associated with the specific interactions present, we argue. Only in the special case of $q=1$ do these become the degeneracies of permuting $n(i)$ identical particles i.e. the \ln of their permutations to have the sum form.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that $\ln(n(i)!) \approx n(i) \ln(n(i))$, using Stirling's approximation for the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, represents a "sum" form of the degeneracy of permuting $n(i)$ identical particles. Thus entropy is a representation of a sum form of degeneracies in a system (with respect to the interactions which occur). We ask whether one may consider more general degeneracies which in a certain limit become the sum form of the degeneracy of permuting $n(i)$ identical particles. The answer seems to be yes and follows from the identity:

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \{ p(i)^x - 1 \} / x = \ln(p(i))$$

If one considers x as being greater than 0 for example, one may write an entropy form which becomes $\sum_i p(i) \ln[p(i)]$ in the $x \rightarrow 0$ limit. This form is called Tsallis entropy and is given by (1); $\text{entropy} / k = 1/(q-1) \{ 1 - \sum_i p(i)^q \}$ where $q-1$ plays the role of x .

The point we wish to make is that the value in $\{ \}$ seems to represent a sum form of the degeneracies in the system, with $q \rightarrow 1$ representing the sum form of the degeneracy of permuting $n(i)$ identical particles i.e. $\ln(n(i)!)$. From the identity of the \ln it seems one may postulate a more general "sum" form of degeneracies (in sum form) based on a fixed power of $p(i)$.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tsallis_entropy